

Data Dictionary (Codebook)

Variable Name	Description	Type	Measurement Level	Coding / Values
Gender	Sex of the patient	Numeric	Nominal	1 = Male, 2 = Female
Jaw	Dental arch affected by partial edentulism	Numeric	Nominal	1 = Maxillary, 2 = Mandibular
Kennedy	Kennedy classification of partial edentulism	Numeric	Ordinal	1 = Class I, 2 = Class II, 3 = Class III, 4 = Class IV
Agegrp	Age group of the patient	Numeric	Ordinal	1 = 20-30, 2 = 31-40, 3 = 41-50, 4 = 51-60, 5 = 61-70, 6 = 71-80